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Petroleum Subsidy Removal And Academic Attainment Of Public Secondary School Students In Delta State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the impact of petroleum subsidy removal on academic attainment of students in public secondary schools in Delta State. The study is guided by three research questions one of which is to ascertain how the removal of petroleum subsidies has affected the financial situation of households with secondary school students in Delta State. The study is hinged on the human capital theory. The population of the study comprised principals and teachers from four hundred and ninety five (495) public secondary schools from the twenty five (25) Local Government Areas in the State. A sample size of 384 respondents obtained by the Cochran Formula and the multistage sampling technique was used for this study. The instrument for data collection is a self-constructed questionnaire entitled 'Questionnaire on Effect of Petroleum Subsidy Removal on Students Academic Achievement' (QEPSRSAA) which was validated by experts in educational management. The result of the analysis of data revealed that the removal of petroleum subsidy has affected the financial situation of households with secondary school students thereby having difficulty in paying for extramural lessons, raising money for school fees, and having to walk to school instead of taking transportation and a large number of students coming late to school. The study recommended amongst others that since there is a direct correlation between petroleum pump price and every other social commodity and amenities as well as students availability for school engagement, Government should seek out other measures of reducing petroleum pump prices to help reduce its impact of students educational attainment.

Keywords:

INTRODUCTION

Petroleum subsidies have long been a subject of concern and debate in Nigeria, a nation endowed with abundant oil reserves. These subsidies have played a pivotal role in shaping the nation's economic landscape, impacting not only the fiscal and energy sectors but also, as this study explores the realm of education. Nigeria's educational system has been a cornerstone of societal development, providing a gateway to opportunities for its diverse population. Thus, the intricate interplay between petroleum subsidies and the academic attainment of public secondary school students in Nigeria is a critical area that deserves attention (Akporehe & Ekwevugbe, 2025)

The nexus between economic policies and education is not a novel concept. Research from other countries has emphasized the importance of economic policies in shaping educational outcomes. Chhibber and Boyce (2001) conducted a comprehensive study on the relationship between economic

policies and education in developing countries. They argued that austerity measures and cuts in public spending, often imposed as part of economic reforms, could negatively affect education, leading to reduced access and quality. This study offers a valuable framework for understanding how economic policy changes can impact education (Imonivwerha, Ekwevugbe & Okandeji, 2011)

Nigeria is often referred to as the "Giant of Africa" due to its population size and oil wealth, has been a significant player in the global oil market. The country's economy is heavily reliant on the petroleum sector, making it one of the largest oil producers in Africa. This economic dependence on oil is closely linked to the government's subsidization of petroleum products, including gasoline and kerosene. Subsidies on petroleum have been a longstanding policy in Nigeria, aimed at maintaining affordable prices for these essential commodities. This has been perceived as a way to ameliorate the financial burden on the populace and to foster socio-economic stability.

However, the sustainability of these subsidies has been a subject of debate, particularly in the context of their fiscal implications. The financial strain on the government, coupled with concerns over corruption and the effective distribution of the subsidy benefits, has led to periodic discussions about their removal. The abrupt withdrawal of these subsidies, as experienced in 2012 and the subsequent partial or full removal in subsequent years, had profound repercussions on various sectors of the Nigerian society (Obadan, 2012; Ajakaiye & Jeroh, 2012)

The Nigerian public education sector plays a pivotal role in the country's development by providing educational opportunities to a diverse and growing population. Public secondary schools, in particular, serve as a vital component of this system, shaping the future of Nigerian youth by equipping them with essential knowledge and skills (Ekwevugbe, 2014)

The sector is significantly influenced by the policies surrounding petroleum and fuel subsidies. Petroleum subsidies, particularly on gasoline and kerosene, have been a longstanding component of Nigeria's economic policies. These subsidies aim to ensure that essential commodities, like fuel, remain affordable for the population. The underlying rationale is to alleviate the financial burden on citizens and maintain socio-economic stability. While the intent behind these subsidies is commendable, the consequences of this system on public secondary schools are multifaceted (Nmadu & Lawal, 2017)

One of the most significant consequences of petroleum subsidies on public secondary schools is the seeming diversion of government revenue. When oil prices are high, and the government provides subsidies, a substantial portion of the national budget is allocated to maintaining artificially low fuel prices. The diversion of these financial resources significantly affects the financing of public services, including education (Okonkwo & Echendu 2015) Another consequence of the subsidy system is the exacerbation of inequality in education access (Uduak, 2021; Ogunleye, 2016).

The Nigerian government has made several attempts to reform its petroleum subsidy system to address these challenges. However, these efforts are frequently met with public resistance and social unrest. The dynamic surrounding subsidy policies is complex, as any significant shift in these policies can lead to economic and social turmoil. Policy decisions related to fuel subsidies require a delicate balancing act, carefully weighing economic realities against public expectations regarding fuel prices (Okafor, 2016)

Balancing the needs of the Nigerian public education sector for adequate funding, access, and quality with the economic constraints related to fuel subsidies is a significant challenge. Sustainable solutions are essential to ensure that public secondary schools receive the necessary resources to enhance infrastructure, improve teacher quality, and raise the overall standard of education. Evidence-based policymaking that considers the long-term consequences on education is vital to support the growth and improvement of Nigeria's public education sector (Ekwevugbe, 2018,; Onodugo et al. 2016)

The study adopted the human capital theory; this is highly relevant when discussing the relationship between economic policies and education. This theory underscores that investments in education and human capital are essential for long-term economic growth and development. In the context of petroleum

subsidy removal, understanding how changes in subsidies affect the human capital development of Nigeria's youth is crucial (Ekwevugbe & Efetobor, 2025)

Problem of the Study

Despite the importance of education, it is undeniable that Nigeria's educational system faces numerous challenges, insufficient funding, inadequate infrastructure, teacher shortages, and outdated curricula are just a few of the persistent issues. The impact of these challenges on academic attainment in public secondary schools has already been a matter of concern (Igwebuike, Okandeji & Ekwevugbe, 2013). With the removal of petroleum subsidies in Nigeria, the economic landscape has undergone significant changes. This policy shift has inevitably affected the cost of living and household expenditure. Students and their families, already grappling with the challenges of education, now find themselves navigating an altered financial terrain. Consequently, the research problem at hand pertains to understanding the perceived impact of petroleum subsidy removal on the academic attainment of public secondary school students in Nigeria. The increased cost of transportation to school, school fees, and the purchase of learning materials can present formidable obstacles to students' continued education

Research Questions

The following research guided the study

1. How has the removal of petroleum subsidies affected the financial situation of households with secondary school students in Delta State?
2. What are the perceived changes in educational expenses and accessibility since the removal of petroleum subsidies on secondary school students in Delta State?
3. To what extent has the changes influenced the academic attainment of public secondary school students in Delta State?

METHOD

Research Design

The research design for this study is the ex-post facto research design. This approach will allow for a comprehensive exploration of the perceived impact of staggered school attendance on students' academic attainment in Nigeria, capturing both numerical data from a range on respondents within the targeted population.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises principals and teachers from four hundred and ninety five (495) public secondary schools from the twenty five (25) Local Government Areas in Delta State, Nigeria, based on the 2023/2024 academic calendar of the Delta State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education. The principals and teachers were targeted from various secondary schools in order to assess the impact of petroleum subsidy removal on academic attainment of public secondary school students in Delta State, especially in this period when the Nigerian economy is experiencing massive increase in petroleum pump prices and general economic recession. The principals and teachers were employed because they had direct control over students in the classroom and also access to students' results and performance reports.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 384 respondents was used for this study. It was derived from the Cochran Formula and the multistage sampling technique, which is appropriate for deriving a sample size from a population that is uncertain.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection is a self-made questionnaire entitled 'Questionnaire on Effect of Petroleum Subsidy Removal on Students Academic Achievement' (QEPSRSAA)

To ensure face and content validity, the drafted questionnaire was scrutinized by specialist. The instrument was appraised to ensure that its items were adequate to answer the research questions. The completed questionnaires were collected and analyzed using Pearson's product correlation coefficient, the

resultant value of 0.88 was adjudged reliable for the study. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies, percentages, and means was used to analyze the data.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *How has the removal of petroleum subsidies affected the financial situation of households with secondary school students?*

Table 1. Mean score of the variables on how the removal of petroleum subsidies has affected the financial situation of households with secondary school students

S/No	Teacher attendance scheduling	N	VL E	LE	LW E	VLE	Mean	STD
1	Experience difficulty in paying for extramural lessons	380	112	138	48	82	2.737	1.104
2	Difficulty in raising money for students School Fees	380	128	111	76	65	2.795	1.087
3	Large number of students walk to school instead of taking transportation	380	117	130	50	83	2.739	1.117
4	As a result of walking to school a large number of students come late to school	380	141	122	40	77	2.861	1.127
5	Inadequate provision of textbook and exercise books for students	380	136	110	83	51	2.871	1.049
6	Inadequate provision of snacks and refreshment for students during break time / lunch breaks	380	144	101	55	80	2.813	1.155
Total Mean							2.803	0.058

Key: 0.1-1.25 = Very Low Extent, 1.26 – 2.4 = Low Extent, 2.5 – 3.75 = Large Extent, 3.76 – 4.00 = Very Large Extent

The table (1) displays all variable items regarding how the removal of petroleum subsidies has affected the financial situation of households with secondary school students having mean scores that are above the 2.50 average mean mark, but falling within the 2.5 – 3.75 = Large Extent category. Indicating therefore that to a large extent the removal of petroleum subsidies has affected the financial situation of households with secondary school students by difficulty in paying for extramural lessons, Difficulty in raising money for students School Fees, students walk to school instead of taking transportation, large number of students coming school to late, Inadequate provision of textbook and exercise books for students and Inadequate provision of snacks and refreshment for students during break time / lunch breaks. In addition, the group mean of 2.803±0.058 also falling within the (2.5 – 3.75 = Large Extent) which is clearly above the average mean score of 2.50 highlights the fact that the respondents affirm that to a large extent the removal of petroleum subsidies has affected the financial situation of households with secondary school students in Delta State.

Research Question Two: *What are the perceived changes in educational expenses and accessibility since the removal of petroleum subsidies?*

Table 2. Mean score of the variables on the perceived changes in educational expenses and accessibility since the removal of petroleum subsidies

S/No	Teacher attendance scheduling	N	VHE	LE	LWE	VLE	Mean	STD
1	Parents reduce the frequency and number of lessons attended by their children	380	124	115	63	78	2.750	1.120
2	Parents take their children to cheaper schools	380	142	86	91	61	2.813	1.106
3	Parents relocate their children to Schools that are in close proximity to their homes	380	131	105	65	79	2.758	1.137
4	Parents urge and admonish their children to trek or walk to school	380	155	97	55	73	2.879	1.144
5	Delay in the payment of school fees by parents	380	150	85	98	47	2.889	1.067
6	Parents prepare their children and even urge them to indulge in accelerated promotion to the next class level ahead long before they are academically qualified to be in.	380	158	76	70	76	2.832	1.173
Total Mean							2.820	0.059

Key: 0.1-1.25 = Very Low Extent, 1.26 – 2.4 = Low Extent, 2.5 – 3.75 = Large Extent, 3.76 – 4.00 = Very High Extent

The table (2) highlights all variable items regarding the perceived changes in educational expenses and accessibility since the removal of petroleum subsidies having mean scores that are above the 2.50 mean bench mark, and also falling within the 2.5 – 3.75 = Large Extent mean category. By implication, to a large extent Parents reduce the frequency and number of lessons attended by their children, Parents take their children to cheaper schools, Parents relocate their children to Schools that are in close proximity to their homes, Parents urge and admonish their children to trek or walk to school, Delay in the payment of school fees by parents, and Parents prepare their children and even urge them to indulge in accelerated promotion to the next class level ahead long before they are academically qualified to be in were to a large extent the perceived changes in educational expenses and accessibility since the removal of petroleum subsidies. In addition, the group mean of 2.820 ± 0.059 also falling within the (2.5 – 3.75 = Large Extent) clearly above the average mean score of 2.50 portrays the fact that to a large extent perceived changes exists in educational expenses and accessibility since the removal of petroleum subsidies in Delta State.

Research Question Three: *To what extent has the changes in cost influenced the academic attainment of public secondary school students in Delta State?*

Table 3. Mean score of how the changes influenced the academic attainment of public secondary school students in Delta State

S/No	Teacher attendance scheduling	N	VHE	LE	LWE	VLE	Mean	STD
1	Students sometimes loose class sessions due to school fees drive resulting from parents inability to cope with high schools fees payments	380	121	115	76	68	2.761	1.086
2	Students lack writing materials and text books to actively participate in classroom sessions	380	134	87	98	61	2.774	1.098
3	Students no longer have revision /follow up classes and lessons to prepare them for test, and examinations	380	128	105	73	74	2.755	1.119
4	Students lack concentration in class due to dehydration and lack of refreshments during break times	380	151	96	64	69	2.866	1.130
5	Students easily lose focus due to exhaustion from long walks/trekking to school	380	142	85	110	43	2.858	1.048
6	Students are ill prepared and find it difficult to cope with new class level attained by accelerated	380	154	72	88	66	2.826	1.142
Total Mean							2.807	0.050

Key: 0.1-1.25 = Very Low Extent, 1.26 – 2.4 = Low Extent, 2.5 – 3.75 = Large Extent, 3.76 – 4.00 = Very High Extent

The table (3) showcases all variable items regarding how changes in petroleum subsidy influenced academic attainment of public secondary school students in Delta State with each item having a mean score above the 2.50 mean bench mark, and also within the category of 2.5 – 3.75 = Large Extent mean. As a result, to a large extent Students loose class sessions due to school fees drive resulting from parents inability to cope with high schools fees payments, Students lack writing materials and text books to actively participate in classroom sessions, Students no longer have revision /follow up classes and lessons to prepare them for test, and examinations, Students lack concentration in class due to dehydration and lack of refreshments during break times, and Students are ill prepared and find it difficult to cope with new class level attained by accelerated promotion were some of the effect of the changes in petroleum subsidy that has influenced academic attainment of public secondary school students in Delta State. In addition, the group mean of 2.807 ± 0.050 also within the (2.5 – 3.75 = Large Extent) mean range also above the average mean score of 2.50 correlates to the position of the respondents that to a large extent changes in petroleum subsidy has influenced academic attainment of public secondary school students in Delta State.

DISCUSSION OF RESULT

The study revealed that petroleum subsidy removal has an impact on academic attainment of public secondary school students in Delta State, Nigeria. The study also indicated that to a large extent the removal of petroleum subsidies has affected the financial situation of households with secondary school students by difficulty in paying for extramural lessons, difficulty in raising money for students school fees, students walking to school instead of taking transportation, large number of students coming late to school, Inadequate provision of textbook and exercise books for students and Inadequate provision of snacks / refreshment for students during break time / lunch breaks. In a similar study, Ake (2023) reports that student's loose interest to academic activities due to lack of food and money which is occasioned by

subsidy removal. Ogunode, and Ukozor (2024) explained that these findings unequivocally demonstrate that the removal of subsidies has cast adverse ramifications on education and general access to education, which manifests as amplified operational costs, elevated tuition fees, increased expenses for parents and guardians, resulting into necessitated alterations in order to keep students in school.

Apparently, as Ogunode, and Aregbesola, (2023) explained, that students are at the receiving end of the learning process, and whatever happens affect them directly, as the study reveals that parents reduce the frequency and number of lessons attended by their children, parents take their children to cheaper schools, relocating them to schools that are in close proximity to their homes. The study also showed that a large number of students trek or walk to school, and experience delay in the payment of school fees. While in order to save cost, parents prepare and even urge their children into jumping class levels or gain accelerated promotion to the next class level even before actually being academically sound and qualified for. These were all to a large extent perceived as the changes in educational expenses and accessibility since the removal of petroleum subsidies.

In Conclusion, Hitato (2023) highlights that the removal of fuel subsidy has brought about economic hardships for students and this has had a very significant effect on them as the study shows that to a large extent students loose class sessions due to school fees drive resulting from parents inability to cope with high schools fees payments, students lack writing materials and text books to actively participate in classroom sessions, Students no longer have revision /follow up classes and lessons to prepare them for test, and examinations, Students lack concentration in class due to dehydration and lack of refreshments during break times, and Students are ill prepared and find it difficult to cope with new class level attained by accelerated promotion were some of the effect of the changes in petroleum subsidy that has influenced academic attainment of public secondary school students in Nigeria. Ogunode and Ukozor (2024) clarified that the impact subsidies removal on tertiary institutions in Nigeria includes; increment in operational cost of tertiary institutions, increment in school fess, teaching programme modification and increment operation cost.

Findings

This study examines the impact of petroleum subsidy removal on academic attainment of public secondary school students in delta state. The finding from the study reveals:

1. the removal of petroleum subsidies has to a large extent affected the financial situation of households with secondary school students in Delta State.
2. The perceived changes exist in educational expenses and accessibility since the removal of petroleum subsidies in Delta State includes.
3. to a large extent changes in petroleum subsidy has influenced academic attainment of public secondary school students in Delta State.

CONCLUSION

The research concludes that petroleum subsidy removal has an impact on academic attainment of public secondary school students in Delta State, Nigeria. In concurrence, Offor, & Ego (2024) pointed out that the Subsidy removal has a very negative effect on students of which majority of them have difficulty in paying for extramural lessons, School Fees, and Inadequacy in the provision of textbook and exercise books for class room sessions. The implication of the removal of fuel subsidy is increased fuel prices and cost of food subjecting the students to hardship due to paucity of funds (Okeke, 2023).

RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings and conclusion of this study has led the researcher to make the following recommendations;

1. Since there is a direct correlation between petroleum pump price and every other social commodity and amenities, Government should seek out other measure of reducing petroleum pump prices

2. Government should be responsible for overhead running cost of government owned educational institutions
3. Government should be responsible for overhead running cost of government owned educational institutions

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